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**Aerodynamic study of airfoils and wings
for power kites applications**

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Summary

Kites are flying in the sky since several centuries, but they are generally considered no more than a toy for children. Nevertheless the flight of a kite is a complex physical phenomenon, and scientists periodically show a renewed interest in kites dynamics, investigating new applications or improving the existing ones. Big part of the studies in the recent past regarded the use of kites as a meteorological source of data or, more recently, as sporting goods for extreme athletes, but a new frontier is raising: the clean energy generation.

The Kite Gen project is one of the proposed alternatives to conventional wind farms. The possibility to collect wind energy at high altitude plays a key role in the Kite Gen concept and this challenging task can be achieved with a careful aerodynamic design integrated with the automated flight control.

This work intends to provide a preliminary series of data about arc shaped wings obtained by means of computational fluid dynamics. These data will be used to improve the flight control strategy and will represent a benchmark for direct comparison with the experimentally collected data from the flying field.

The method followed will be extensively described in the next chapters and, hopefully, will be used as a guideline for further simulations and design optimization. In fact, the commercially available power kites are designed with the different purpose of dragging people riding on surf boards or buggies, and they are limited in terms of dimensions, structural resistance and performances by the pilot's weight and strength.

The high altitude wind energy conversion into electric power will need a new generation of kites, expressly designed to grant the peak efficiency of the process and the necessary safety and reliability on duty.

Italian abstract

The Italian abstract has been enclosed in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Dottore Magistrale in Ingegneria Aerospaziale at Politecnico di Torino

Studio aerodinamico di profili alari e ali per applicazioni su aquiloni di potenza

Prefazione Gli aquiloni solcano il cielo da centinaia di anni, ma sono generalmente considerati poco più di un gioco per fanciulli. Nonostante questo il volo di un aquilone è un fenomeno fisico complesso e periodicamente gli scienziati mostrano un rinnovato interesse nella dinamica degli aquiloni, studiando nuove possibili applicazioni o migliorando quelle esistenti.

Il progetto KiteGen è una delle alternative proposte agli impianti eolici convenzionali. La possibilità di catturare l'energia del vento in alta quota gioca un ruolo chiave nel funzionamento del KiteGen e questo ambizioso traguardo può essere raggiunto con un attento progetto aerodinamico integrato con il controllo automatico del volo.

Questo lavoro intende fornire una serie di dati preliminari, ottenuti con i metodi della fluidodinamica computazionale, sul comportamento di ali a forma di arco,. Gli stessi dati saranno utilizzati per migliorare la strategia di controllo automatico del volo e rappresenteranno un termine di paragone diretto per i dati sperimentali acquisiti nel corso delle prove di volo.

La metodologia adottata sarà ampiamente descritta e auspicabilmente usata come linea guida per ulteriori simulazioni e per l'ottimizzazione del progetto. Infatti, gli aquiloni di potenza disponibili in commercio sono progettati col differente obiettivo di trascinare persone su tavole da surf o dune buggy, e sono vincolati in termini di dimensioni, resistenza strutturale e prestazioni dal peso e dalla forza del pilota.

Per la conversione di energia eolica d'alta quota in energia elettrica si renderà necessaria una nuova generazione di aquiloni, appositamente progettati per garantire il massimo rendimento del processo e le necessarie sicurezza e affidabilità durante il servizio.

Introduzione L'evoluzione morfologica degli aquiloni di potenza e i brevetti che ne hanno determinato il corso sono brevemente illustrati, così come una descrizione delle metodologie costruttive attuali e dei materiali impiegati. Vengono introdotte le caratteristiche peculiari del volo di un aquilone di potenza e citate le fonti che descrivono le diverse metodologie di misura delle prestazioni.

Il progetto KiteGen è descritto nei suoi aspetti fondamentali e i risultati di una tipica simulazione sono presentati. Dall'analisi di questi risultati si evincono le motivazioni che hanno portato al presente lavoro, ovvero la necessità di modellizzare accuratamente le caratteristiche aerodinamiche di un aquilone a forma di arco e studiare l'effetto che le regolazioni di assetto esercitano sull'efficienza aerodinamica. L'efficienza aerodinamica rappresenta infatti uno dei parametri che maggiormente influenzano il rendimento del generatore eolico KiteGen.

Il codice STAR-CCM+ Il codice commerciale STAR-CCM+, disponendo di un'ampia gamma di modelli matematici e di solutori numerici, permette la simulazione termofluidodinamica di problemi complessi. Le caratteristiche del codice maggiormente utilizzate in questo lavoro vengono descritte brevemente. Poiché il codice richiede la discretizzazione del dominio di calcolo mediante volumi finiti, viene descritta in dettaglio una strategia di generazione delle griglie di calcolo che si è rivelata efficiente. Viene infine motivata la scelta del modello di turbolenza Spalart-Allmaras utilizzato nelle simulazioni.

Casistica di prova Viene data prova del corretto utilizzo del software tramite la simulazione di problemi di aerodinamica esterna. È stato simulato il flusso bidimensionale stazionario turbolento ad alto numero di Reynolds attorno ai profili alari NACA 0012, NACA 2412 e Clark Y standard, inoltre per il solo profilo NACA 0012 è stato simulato il flusso bidimensionale laminare. È stato infine simulato il flusso tridimensionale stazionario turbolento ad alto numero di Reynolds intorno a un'ala rettangolare avente profilo Clark Y standard e aspect ratio 6. La scelta degli studi preliminari si è basata sul criterio di utilizzare casi ampiamente documentati in letteratura. Una interpretazione ragionata dei risultati ottenuti è proposta per i singoli casi.

Il modello di aquilone Il modello di ala, avente profilo Clark Y, è ampiamente descritto nelle sue caratteristiche geometriche ed è, se pure con evidenti semplificazioni, assimilabile ad alcune tipologie di aquiloni disponibili in commercio. L'effetto sulle caratteristiche aerodinamiche della curvatura nel piano frontale tipica degli aquiloni a forma di arco è stato studiato e messo in evidenza partendo dalla simulazione di un modello di ala rettangolare. Il modello originario è stato successivamente modificato attribuendo una curvatura ad arco di cerchio nel piano frontale e studiato in dettaglio. I risultati del calcolo dei coefficienti di portanza, resistenza e momento del modello finale di aquilone sono presentati, analizzati e accompagnati da considerazioni sul comportamento dopo lo stallo dell'ala.

Equilibrio statico longitudinale La determinazione dei punti di equilibrio longitudinale in condizioni stazionarie, in funzione della geometria dell'imbrigliatura dell'aquilone, è stata condotta adattando al caso specifico un modello noto in letteratura. Le differenze nell'assetto di volo che si verificano considerando valori differenti della velocità del vento sono state evidenziate. Dalla loro analisi è stata formulata una proposta di regolazione

dell'assetto di volo in funzione del campo di variazione della velocità del vento previsto in sede di progetto.

Conclusioni I risultati presentati, sebbene ottenuti facendo l'ipotesi di condizioni di flusso e di moto stazionarie, rappresentano un passo necessario verso la comprensione del comportamento dinamico degli aquiloni di potenza e possono già essere utilizzati per migliorare il modello sviluppato per simulare il controllo automatico del generatore eolico KiteGen. La metodologia seguita può essere utilizzata con successo per studiare modelli di aquilone più complessi, ad esempio considerando gli effetti della rastrematura, dell'angolo di freccia e dello svergolamento. Future analisi dovranno riguardare l'influenza che i cavi esercitano sul volo e sul controllo dell'aquilone, non considerata in questo lavoro ma di grande importanza nel caso di cavi molti lunghi. Questi ed altri studi saranno fondamentali per comprendere se sia più conveniente, in termini di massima potenza media generata dal KiteGen, utilizzare aquiloni in grado di volare ad alta velocità in corrispondenza di un basso coefficiente di portanza o, al contrario, a bassa velocità e alto coefficiente di portanza.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The engine of the KiteGen wind generator are power kites. The first step to understand how KiteGen can convert wind energy into electric energy is examining the kites flight mechanics and their aerodynamic characteristics.

In this chapter we will briefly report the evolution and the state of the art in power kites design and manufacturing, then we will describe the general outlines of the KiteGen project.

1.1 Traction kites

1.1.1 Brief history of traction kites

The use of traction kites for recreational use is relatively recent. Between the fathers of modern kites we must cite first of all Domina Jalbert, who invented in the middle 60's the parafoil [16], successfully trying to improve parachute's performance. The concept at the basis of the parafoil is that a large air inlet at the leading edge of an inflatable wing and a small air outlet help to maintain the canopy in the desired aerodynamic shape. Even if the original purpose of the parafoil was to suspend payloads in captive flight or to recover payloads from space, the concept was soon adopted for traction kites.

In fact, just a few years later, Jones and Merry invented what has been commercially called Flexifoil[®]. Their patent [17] describes a tethered ram air kite with two control lines and a flexible spar at the leading edge. The use of the spar was progressively abandoned when the aerodynamic knowledge and experience of the competing designers grew up. Even if the ram air kites are still the preferred choice to drag dune buggies and snowboards, they can't be employed for water sports.

Another big step came when the Legaigoux brothers solved in 1984 the problem with the invention of the leading edge inflatable kite (LEI) [19]. After years of continuous improvements, in 2004 they applied for a new patent describing the next generation of LEI kites, calling them BOW kites [20].

1.1.2 Ram air traction kites

The evolution of the original Flexifoil® design is still flying and is greatly appreciated for the huge amount of pull that it can generate. A draft is presented in Fig. 1.1 and the extremely interesting possibility to add more and more kites to a single couple of control lines is shown in Fig. 1.2.

Figure 1.1. Ram air kite with LE spar- Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

Figure 1.2. Stack of ram air kites with LE spar- Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

A modern ram air traction kite is shown in Fig. 1.3. The big air inlets at the leading edge are clearly visible. To maintain the shape of the wing a very complex bridle system is needed. The number of control lines was originally limited to a couple, then it has been progressively increased up to 5. The basic configuration with two lines gives the pilot only a directional control so that the kite can be steered and maneuvered pulling alternatively the lines. With the additional control lines a good control on the kite angle of attack is achievable, so that the pilot can reduce or increase the lift accordingly to the wind conditions.

Figure 1.3. Ram air kite - Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

1.1.3 Leading edge inflatable kites

The LEI kite family has a series of inflatable bladders, so that an extremely light wing can assume a certain amount of structural stiffness limiting the deformations under the flight loads which greatly affect the kite shape.

Anyway, the most experienced designers of flexible materials, like sails, kites and tensile structures, are somehow able to predict these deformations and they generally create structures that will assume the desired flying shape when loaded.

In spite of the enormous advantage due to the stiffness, the flow in the boundary layer can easily detach from the wing lower surface because of the unconventional wing section. The designers trade-off is currently trying to reduce to a minimum the leading edge structure diameter. A sample of LEI kite is shown in Fig. 1.4.

Figure 1.4. LEI kite - Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

1.1.4 BOW kites

To describe the BOW kites, we directly quote the inventors explanation “the BOW concept consists in giving some sweep to the kite wing to flatten its trailing edge then flattening the leading edge in a mechanical way to match the shape of the trailing edge and thus obtaining a flatter wing with large depower”.

The term “depower” refers to the pilot capability to suddenly reduce the lift maintaining the kite control when dangerous conditions arise (gusts, obstacles, manoeuvring errors). A sample of BOW kite is shown in Fig. 1.5.

Figure 1.5. BOW kite - Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

1.1.5 Materials

The construction materials of modern kites are obviously based on manmade fibers. The canopy is generally made with polyamide (Nylon[®]) fabric woven in a ripstop fashion, but some manufacturers also use polyester fabric. These light but tear resistant fabrics are coated with resins to reduce the air permeability. For the inflatable models, the bladders are generally made with polyurethane and the valves are electrically bonded to the bladders. The bladders of the leading edge and of the struts are covered with high tenacity polyester fabric (Dacron[®]), while reinforcements made of bullet-proof aramid fabric (Kevlar[®]) can be used to prevent impact damages. The final assembly can be made stitching or thermally sealing. Finally, the control lines are generally braided with high modulus fibers like Dyneema[®], so that the line section is small and the parasite drag of the lines is reduced to a minimum.

1.1.6 Typical dimensions

Power kites dimensions are limited by the weight and by the strength of the pilot, so the surface can vary from 2 – 3 m² of a trainer model to 18 – 20 m² of a LEI model for light wind. The mass of kites can vary between 2 – 4 kg.

1.1.7 Traction kite's flight

A kite can only fly in a limited portion of the sky called the “wind window”. The wind window is shown in Fig. 1.6. The breadth of the wind window is determined by the kite's aerodynamic characteristics. Moreover, the kite behavior greatly changes according to the zone of the wind window where is flying.

At the top of the wind window, exactly above the pilot's head, there's the zenith position. When the kite is flying at the zenith, it only does small moving respect to the ground prescribed by changes in the wind speed and direction. In this case the air speed relative to the wing almost coincides with the wind speed. For this reason, the kite can rest at the zenith position exerting a minimum pull on the control lines.

At the contrary, when the kite is flying downwind in front of the pilot, the kite speed relative to the ground can be extremely high. Since the air speed relative to the kite is the vectorial sum of the wind speed and of the kite speed, and the aerodynamic resultant is proportional to the air speed relative to the kite squared, flying a traction kite in a figure of eight trough this part of the wind window can result in an enormous pull on the control lines. For this reason the kites call it the “power zone”. The air speed relative to the kite is often called “apparent wind” or “effective wind speed”, and is the same experienced by the sails of a sailing yacht. From seamanship we know that “There's nothing more real than the apparent wind”.

1.1.8 Flight tests

The experimental measure of power kites performances it's all but an easy task. One of the first work we can refer to has been published by Hobbs [11]. More recently Stevenson

and Alexander, with the contribution of the designer Peter Lynn, undertook a systematic research work on testing procedures, starting with a car test rig [3], and introducing later new methods like the circular flight kite test (see [28] and [29]).

From these papers we learn that a typical traction kite like the old but representative C-Quad model (Peter Lynn Kites) can be tuned to fly with a lift coefficient varying approximately from 0,65 to 0,8 and a lift to drag ratio varying from 4,6 to 5,1.

These values are greatly dependant from the followed test method, but they suggest us the magnitude of the involved quantities.

Figure 1.6. The wind window - Courtesy Flexifoil International Ltd

Finally, we found in a recent work presented by Jackson [13] one of the clearer and interesting explanations about the tendencies of arc shaped kites to align themselves normal to the wind, so that we decided to quote his words:

“The Kutta-Joukowski forces acting near the ends of the kite are directed horizontally and normal to the wind, so that if the kite yaws about a vertical axis these forces provide a restoring moment that it turns it back again. We may presume that the same forces are responsible for the deliberate turning of a kite by means of the control lines. If the kite is “rolled” by pulling down on one line, the net lift force must rotate toward that side, causing the kite to begin moving sideways in that direction. This adds a component of incident wind so that apparent wind comes from the side to which the kite is swaying, and the action of the forces described earlier turns the kite to face the same way.”

1.2 The KiteGen project

The concepts at the basis of the KiteGen project have been published and presented during several international conferences, the interested reader can find the full text in [7] and [8] and also refer to the original patents [27] and [26] , while here we will only reproduce the contents necessary to understand the KiteGen project.

We start describing the first working prototype, solidly anchored to the body of a vehicle:

“The key idea is to capture wind energy by means of tethered airfoils whose flight is suitably driven by an automatic control unit. In the first step of the KiteGen project a small scale prototype has been realized (see Fig. 1.7) to show the capability of controlling the flight of a single kite, by pulling the two lines which hold it, in such a way to extract a significant amount of energy. In the configuration considered in [7], indicated as “yo-yo” configuration, the Kite Steering Unit (KSU)(see Fig. 1.8) has two electric actuators which act as motors in pulling the lines for controlling the flight or for recovering the kite and as generators if the line length increases when pulled by the kite. The electric actuators which hold the lines are fixed respect to the ground. Energy is generated by continuously repeating a cycle composed of two phases: the traction and the recovery ones. In the traction phase the control is designed such that the kite pulls the lines, so that a certain amount of energy is generated. When the maximal length of the lines is reached, the control enters into the recovery phase, and a new traction phase is undertaken”.

Using a *carousel* configuration, the potentialities of the KiteGen can further increase:

“In such configuration, several airfoils are controlled by their KSU placed on the arms of a vertical axis rotor (see Fig. 1.9), and the control is designed to maximize the power transmitted by the airfoils to the rotor, suitably connected to an electric generator. The torque opposed to the motion by the electric generator is suitably controlled in order to keep the rotation speed constant. Energy is generated by continuously repeating a cycle composed of two phases, the traction and the drag ones. These phases are related to the angular position Θ of the control unit, with respect to the wind direction (see Fig. 1.10). During the traction phase, which begins at $\Theta = \Theta_3$, the control is designed in such a way that the kite pulls the rotor, maximizing the generated power. This phase ends at $\Theta = \Theta_0$ and the drag phase begins: the kite is no more able to generate a positive power until angle Θ reaches the value Θ_3 . In this phase, the control is designed to move the kite, with as low energy as possible, in the suitable position to begin another traction phase, where once again the control is designed to maximize the generated power. The control design is here carried on using a Fast implementation of a Predictive Controller (FMPC)”.

Figure 1.7. KiteGen small scale prototype

Figure 1.8. Kite Steering Unit

Figure 1.9. Carousel configuration of KiteGen

Figure 1.10. Carousel configuration phases

1.3 Aim of the present work

We will not deal with the kite generator model and with the kite control using FMPC, being this subjects just extensively explained in the cited papers, but we will briefly examine some simulation results. Starting from these data, the reasons which moved us to undertake this research work and the new results we were looking for will be clear.

We simply introduce the lift and drag coefficients, usually defined as

$$C_L = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}$$

and

$$C_D = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}$$

We also define the effective wind speed \vec{W}_e

$$\vec{W}_e = \vec{W}_a - \vec{W}_l$$

where \vec{W}_a is the kite speed expressed in a local system centered in the kite center of gravity and \vec{W}_l is the wind vector (see [8] for details). The \vec{W}_e value must be entered in place of V when calculating C_L and C_D .

In Table I are shown some of the model and control parameters used for a typical simulation with a nominal wind speed equals to 8 m/s at 0 m of height and 17 m/s at 300 m. A sample of simulated trajectory is presented in Fig. 1.11, while Fig. 1.12 and Fig. 1.13 respectively show the generated power and the effective wind speed during two cycles.

m	50	kite mass (kg)
A	100	characteristics area (m ²)
r_0	300	line length (m)
J_z	$9 \cdot 10^8$	rotor moment of inertia (kg m ²)
R	300	rotor radius (m)
ρ	1.2	air density (kg m ³)
C_L	1.2	lift coefficient
C_D	0.15	drag coefficient
$\dot{\Theta}_{ref}$	0.16	reference $\dot{\Theta}$ (rpm)
T_c	0.2	sample time (s)
N_c	1	control horizon (steps)
N_p	8	prediction horizon (steps)

Table I. Model and control parameters

Accordingly to the simplified kite model presented by Diehl [9], a constant lift coefficient and a constant drag coefficient have been considered. Variable lift and drag

coefficients are probably one of the major improvements needed to the future models, so we intend to determine the aerodynamic coefficients of a representative kite wing and to investigate how these coefficients vary in reply to wind speed changes and to bridles configuration.

The effective wind speed magnitude $|\vec{W}_e|$ calculated during the simulations is impressive (see Fig. 1.13), often exceeding 70 m/s, and we know from the top kite designers that high speeds can be only achieved flying trough the power zone with extremely efficient kites. But we also know from finite wing theory and from experimental results that the maximum efficiency L/D for conventional wings occurs at low absolute angle of attack and low lift coefficient C_L , so the knowledge of an accurate aerodynamic efficiency curve is fundamental to look for the optimum kite trim that grants the maximum electric power generation.

Examining the size of the kite characteristic area and its weight, it's pretty clear that the simulated model is definitely bigger than any commercially available power kite. Even if kites of bigger dimensions commonly fly during kites exhibition, they are designed for recreational use. Huge kites to generate power will require more than an accurate aerodynamic design, they will probably need fluid structure interaction analysis, advanced materials and hi-tech manufacturing processes.

Figure 1.11. Kite (thin line) and control unit trajectory with nominal conditions: *traction phase* (solid) and *drag phase* (dot-dash)

Figure 1.12. Instant (solid) and mean (dashed) power generated during two cycles, nominal conditions

Figure 1.13. Effective wind speed magnitude $|\vec{W}_e|$, nominal conditions

Chapter 2

The STAR-CCM+ CFD code

The STAR-CCM+ software is a commercially available multi-physics code based on computational continuum mechanics algorithms. We will describe in this chapter a limited number of STAR-CCM+ features, focusing only on the specific settings and procedures that help understanding the work done. More details are extensively reported in the STAR-CCM+ user guide.

2.1 Problem setting

Continuum

The representation of the simulated substance (fluid or solid) is treated by STAR-CCM+ as a collection of models called continuum. The interesting feature is that continua can be defined independently of the mesh. The user can enable the desired models within a continuum accordingly to the physical nature of the simulated problem. The continuum also contains the reference values and the initial conditions.

Models

A model consists in a mathematical representation of a physical phenomenon through a set of equations involving several variables. Complex models equations, like the ones typically used in fluid dynamics, generally need to be solved with numerical methods. The initial conditions and the reference values greatly affect the solution.

Types

The kind of representation of physical regions and boundaries must be defined associating them a type, so a region could be modeled as a fluid or a solid region while a boundary could be a wall or a symmetry plane. We made extensive use of the following boundary types:

free-stream the free-stream represents the boundary of a bubble of fluid surrounding an object flying through space, can be used for external aerodynamic simulations;

symmetry plane a symmetry plane boundary represents an imaginary plane of symmetry in the simulation;

wall a wall boundary represents an impermeable surface. It can be used to represent impermeable, no-slip boundary for viscous fluid flow simulations.

Conditions

Every region or boundary type can be further defined setting its condition. For instance the no-slip condition can be assigned to a wall boundary type, while the physical flow direction specification can be assigned to a free-stream boundary type.

Values

The values specify the actual numerical input of a certain condition, for instance it's possible to set the value of the Mach number and of the static temperature for a free-stream boundary type.

2.2 Meshing

STAR-CCM+ uses the Finite Volume Method (FVM), so the geometrical properties of the bodies involved in the problem must be represented by a mathematical description called volume mesh. The volume mesh is based on different entities like vertices, faces and cells. Without examining in depth the definition of this entities, we must point out the not trivial STAR-CCM+ capability to manage cells of arbitrary polyhedral shape.

Regions and boundaries

The simulated geometrical space can be divided in several regions. Each region must be represented by a volume mesh. The surfaces enclosing a region are called boundaries.

CAD data

The geometrical description of the regions and of their boundaries can be generated and imported as CAD data. Several CAD data format are supported by STAR-CCM+ and we found practical to employ the .stp file format (Standardized Exchange of Product File).

Since the volume mesh of the space surrounding a wing section or a finite span wing model needs to be extremely fine in close proximity of the leading edge and of the trailing edge, while it could be a little more coarse on the middle of the upper and lower surfaces, we developed a strategy that can be easily repeated when changing the airfoil model. We found efficient to split the wing model in several zones just during the CAD design, so that during the import phase these geometrical zones can be considered like different bodies within the same region and they are suitable to generate a good quality volume mesh with the desired zone-dependant resolution. Some options are available when importing the data, we needed to choose the following settings to achieve our goal:

Boundary Mode: one boundary per face;

Region Mode: one region for all bodies;

Mark Feature Edges: all edges.

2.2.1 Meshing models

STAR-CCM+ can create meshes adopting several meshing models. First of all a surface mesh must be created for the continuum regions, then a volume mesh can be generated. For all the simulated cases, we chose the **surface wrapper** and the **surface remesher** models to create the surface mesh, then the **trimmer volume mesher** and the **prism layers mesher**.

The mesh characteristics are influenced by several parameters which can be defined at a region and at a boundary level. We mainly used the boundary level, setting different values in each zone. It has been possible to generate good quality meshes primarily acting on the following parameters:

Base Size: the base size is a characteristic dimension of the model which can be used as a reference to set relative sizes;

Number of Prism Layers: for each boundary surface several layers can be extruded and their number can be set with this parameter;

Prism Layer Thickness: this parameter controls the thickness of the prism layer;

Surface Min/Max size: it defines the bounds of the element dimensions;

Surface Target size: it defines the desired element dimension;

Surface Curvature: it defines the number of points around a circle

2D volume mesh generation

With STAR-CCM+ the simulation of a two-dimensional flow past a wing section however requires a 2D volume mesh with unitary depth. As a first option, it's possible to import a 3D CAD geometry and generate a 3D volume mesh that will be transformed into a 2D volume mesh, and it is the procedure we applied. As an alternative, a 2D mesh with unitary depth can be imported from other grid generator softwares.

In this case, the CAD geometry has been generated creating a finite wing with the span coincident with the width of the parallelepiped representing the computational domain. Since limiting the computational domain width along the Z axis results in a fast 3D volume mesh generation, we used a 15 percent of the chord width in the Z direction. We just anticipated that in the original CAD geometry the finite span wing have been divided in several entities, so that importing the model into STAR-CCM+ results in several boundaries. A sample of the global and custom settings used to generate a 3D mesh is presented in Table II and Table III.

In this case we have a leading edge boundary, an upper and a lower front boundaries, an upper and a lower rear boundaries, a trailing edge boundary and six boundaries describing the control volume.

The global settings generally apply to all the boundaries, but they are superseded when custom settings are defined for a particular boundary. First of all, a Base Size equal to the airfoil chord has been set. A powerful tool called **volume source** has also been extensively used. The volume source allows to define a portion of the model volume where the generated mesh elements must assume the user defined size. In this case, two box shaped volume sources completely surrounding the wing have been used.

Examining the custom settings, it can be seen that a high surface curvature parameter and a very low target size have been set for the leading edge boundary, as well as a low target size has been set for the trailing edge boundary.

Global settings	
Base size	1 m
Number of prism layers	6
Prism layer thickness	1% of base
Surface curvature	72 Pts/circle
Surface size relative min	1% of base
Surface size relative target size	1% of base
Volume sources 1	1% of base
Volume sources 2	0,5% of base

Table II. Global meshing parameters to generate a 3D volume mesh

Custom settings		
Leading edge	Surface curvature	200 Pts/circle
	Surface size relative min	0,1% of base
	Surface size relative target size	0,2% of base
Front (upper and lower)	Surface curvature	200 Pts/circle
	Surface size relative min	0,2% of base
	Surface size relative target size	0,5% of base
Rear (upper and lower)	Surface size relative min	0,2% of base
	Surface size relative target size	0,5% of base
Trailing edge	Surface size relative min	0,1% of base
	Surface size relative target size	0,2% of base

Table III. Custom meshing parameters to generate a 3D volume mesh

The resulting 3D volume mesh has 353 100 cells, 1 036 157 interior faces, 419 504 vertices and is shown in Fig. 2.1. From the 3D volume mesh generated with the described technique a 2D volume mesh can finally be extracted. The two-dimensional airfoil model

resides in a rectangular computational domain, whose upstream and downstream boundaries are located at 3 and 6 chord lengths from the leading edge respectively. The upper and lower boundaries are placed at 3 chord lengths each from the leading edge. Even if the domain dimensions are little, after performing some tests with a bigger domain it has been considered a good compromise between computational cost and accuracy to run the preliminary test cases. The extracted 2D mesh has 30 105 cells, 59 957 interior faces and 30 926 vertices.

The final result is presented in Fig. 2.2, where the effect of the two box shaped volume sources one inside the other is evident, so that a gradual coarsening of the mesh has been obtained. In Fig. 2.3 are clearly visible the brick layer and the fine mesh in the leading edge zone.

Figure 2.1. Wing 3D volume mesh suitable to generate a 2D mesh

3D volume mesh generation for 3D flow simulations

The simulation of the three-dimensional flow past a finite span wing, if the free stream direction lies in the model symmetry plane, can be made designing only one half of the wing and enclosing it within a parallelepiped representing the computational domain. Since the wing shares its symmetry plane with one of the computational domain sides, this side must be defined as a symmetry plane boundary type. A sample of wing CAD model is shown in Fig. 2.4.

In this case a bigger computational domain has been used to grant a better accuracy of the simulation results. The three-dimensional wing model resides in a box shaped

Figure 2.2. Airfoil 2D volume mesh

Figure 2.3. Airfoil 2D volume mesh, detail of the leading edge

Figure 2.4. CAD wing model and computational domain to generate a 3D volume mesh

computational domain, whose upstream and downstream boundaries are located at 3 and 6 chord lengths from the leading edge respectively. The upper and lower boundaries are placed at 5 chord lengths each from the leading edge. The lateral boundary is located at 3 chord lengths from the wing tip. The resulting 3D volume mesh has 2 052 721 cells, 6 232 552 interior faces, 2 421 189 vertices and is shown in Fig. 2.5.

2.3 Modeling

2.3.1 Space, Time and Motion

The selected space model can obviously be the Two-Dimensional Model when simulating the flow past an airfoil, while it must be the Three-Dimensional Model when the flow is past a wing. Even if STAR-CCM+ can manage steady or unsteady time models, we always used the Steady Model for the simulations presented in this work. STAR-CCM+

Figure 2.5. Wing 3D volume mesh

can also consider a Rigid Body Motion Model or a Moving Reference Frame Model , but we always used the Stationary Model since we considered the airfoil or the wing stationary and the free stream moving at the apparent wind speed.

2.3.2 Flow model

We chose the Viscous Flow Model, which can be used for both laminar and turbulent flows. Viscous flows are governed by the Navier-Stokes equations, and when considering turbulent flows, STAR-CCM+ solves the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations.

The RANS equations need to define a turbulence model. We chose the Standard Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model because it has been originally formulated to simulate attached boundary layers and flows with mild separation, like it can be the case for the flow past a wing.

2.3.3 Boundary conditions

The appropriate boundary conditions must be set before running the simulation.

For the Wall boundaries, the no-slip wall conditions must be selected, so that the tangential velocity is set to zero.

For the Symmetry Plane boundary no action is required, since the shear stress is set to zero while velocity, pressure and temperature are extrapolated from the adjacent cells.

For the Free-Stream boundaries the relevant parameters are velocity, temperature and pressure.

Since our goal is modeling the flow past a wing for different values of the angle of attack α , two options are available to set the desired free stream direction. It could be possible to rotate the wing about the Z axis, maintaining the same computational domain and the free stream direction aligned to the X axis, like it's commonly done during wind tunnel testing, but it's definitely more efficient to rotate the free stream wind direction. In fact, in the first case a new mesh should be generated for every angle of attack, while the second option needs only a certain care when calculating the lift and drag coefficient, because the lift and drag direction are directly related to the free stream direction.

2.4 Final remarks

We introduced the fundamental elements to understand how the results presented in this work have been obtained and to interpret the reported values. Particular settings will be put in evidence and analyzed case by case in the following chapters.

Chapter 3

Test Cases

It's common and good practice, using for the first time a commercial CFD code, to compare the results provided by the code with some well documented and recognized test cases. The available data for direct comparison can be experimental, theoretical or CFD results. We chose to test three wing sections in the two-dimensional flow conditions and a finite span wing in three-dimensional flow conditions before running the actual kite's shape simulation.

In this chapter we will describe the geometry, the simulated flow conditions and the results for the following cases, supplying direct comparison with published experimental and CFD results:

- NACA 0012 wing section
- NACA 2412 wing section
- Clark Y standard wing section
- Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6

3.1 The NACA 0012 wing section

The NACA 0012 is probably the more extensively tested and studied wing section, 2D and 3D test cases based on the NACA 0012 airfoil are currently used for CFD codes validation, like for instance the AGARD test cases [10]. The big amount of available data in several different flow conditions suggest to employ the NACA 0012 as a benchmark to set up a new problem with similar flow and boundary conditions. Reaching a set of consistent results in a range of flow conditions gives a preliminary level of confidence in the proper use of the necessary code settings to model the physics of the problem in the right way.

The NACA 0012 is a symmetrical wing section having a maximum thickness equal to the 12% of the chord located at the 30% of the chord.

The Table IV shows the ordinates and the Fig. 3.1 reproduces the NACA 0012 wing section profile.

Upper surface		Lower surface	
Station	Ordinate	Station	Ordinate
0	0	0	0
0,50	1,222	0,50	-1,222
1,25	1,894	1,25	-1,894
2,50	2,615	2,50	-2,615
5,00	3,555	5,00	-3,555
7,50	4,200	7,50	-4,200
10	4,683	10	-4,683
15	5,345	15	-5,345
20	5,738	20	-5,738
25	5,941	25	-5,941
30	6,002	30	-6,002
40	5,803	40	-5,803
50	5,294	50	-5,294
60	4,563	60	-4,563
70	3,664	70	-3,664
80	2,623	80	-2,623
90	1,448	90	-1,448
95	0,807	95	-0,807
100	0,126	100	-0,126

L.E. radius: 1,58

Table iv. NACA 0012 airfoil section, stations and ordinates given in percent of airfoil chord

Figure 3.1. NACA 0012 airfoil

3.1.1 Experimental data source and interpretation

There are several experimental data sources providing different values for the force coefficients acting on the NACA 0012 airfoil in similar conditions. The differences are related to wind tunnel side walls interference, instruments calibration, wind tunnel turbulence,

model surface finishing, supports interference and many other factors. A comprehensive comparative study about experimental data quality is presented by McCroskey[24], where the published data by Abbott & Doenhoff [2] are still considered within the best available.

The kite’s relative velocity range of interest in this work let us completely neglect the effects of Mach number on the force coefficients, nevertheless these effects shall be kept in account if a new class of high speed kites should be built in the next future.

On the other hand, the effects of Reynolds number are of primary importance, being the kite’s geometrical dimensions extremely variable. We shall therefore expect a growth of the maximum section lift coefficient c_{lmax} and increasing lift curve slope $c_{l\alpha}$ with increasing Reynolds number.

The surface finishing is probably the most important factor to be kept in account performing the actual kite simulation. A smooth surface leads to a natural transition between laminar and turbulent flow within the boundary layer, being the location and the effects of this transition a function of the Reynolds number and of the angle of attack α . In smooth surface conditions at a given Reynolds number, the majority of airfoils reaches the highest values of maximum section lift coefficient c_{lmax} and the lowest values of minimum section drag coefficient c_{dmin} .

Unfortunately, the smooth surface condition seems to be unrealistic for a commercially available power kite for factors like fabric characteristics and for the presence of seams, patches, reinforcements all over the kite’s surface. The inherent kite surface roughness suggests to model a fully developed turbulent flow in the boundary layer, but the uncertainty about the actual roughness amount needs further remarks. Even if it could be done, it’s outside the purview of the present work to accurately measure the surface roughness of several kite models.

There are some different methods to force the boundary layer turbulent transition during wind tunnel testing, we will briefly describe the ones extensively used by NACA and NASA.

The first method is based on the standard roughness application. The standard roughness consists of 0,011 inch diameter (0,2794 mm) carborundum grains spread over a surface length of 8 percent of the chord measured from the leading edge on the upper and lower surfaces of the airfoils. The grains are thinly spread to cover from 5 to 10 percent of this area, see Loftin and Smith [22] for details.

This results in a turbulent boundary layer which increases the $c_d - \alpha$ curves but greatly affects the c_{lmax} and α_{st} values compared to the natural transition condition.

The second method is called boundary layer tripping. We learn from Ladson [18], Braslow and Knox [5], that it can be done applying carborundum strips to both the model upper and lower surfaces at the 0,05c station. The strips are 0,01c in width. The carborundum grit size varies with test Reynolds number to provide enough height to trip the boundary layer but not add incremental drag. This again increases the $c_d - \alpha$ curves, but it doesn’t affect the c_{lmax} and α_{st} values as much as the first method.

We can consider this second method close to what can be simulated by the STAR-CCM+ solver setting a fully turbulent flow but a smooth airfoil surface.

All the presented STAR-CCM+ results in the prosecution of this work can be interpreted as the maximum attainable values of c_{lmax} (C_{Lmax} for the finite span wing) and

α_{st} by a real kite with the surface roughness reduced to a minimum. We should expect that the commercially available kites show a similar $c_{l\alpha}$ slope but reduced c_{lmax} and α_{st} values, following the behavior of the presented experimental curves in standard roughness condition.

3.1.2 STAR-CCM+ simulation settings and results

In this first case, a fully turbulent flow past a NACA 0012 section was modeled, from $\alpha = 0^\circ$ to $\alpha = 20^\circ$ in the following conditions:

$$Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$$

$$\rho = 1,225 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\text{chord} = 1 \text{ m}$$

$$V_\infty = 43,86 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\mu = 1,79 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$$

$$p = 1,01325 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$T = 288,2 \text{ K}$$

2D steady and stationary viscous flow

Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model

smooth wall surface, no-slip

mesh size 30 105 volume cells

The simulation results in terms of the aerodynamic section lift coefficient, section drag coefficient and efficiency are shown in Table v

As can be seen, approaching the stall condition the number of iterations has been increased to grant the solution convergence. This strategy has been adopted for all the following cases in the present work. The results have been compared with the experimental measures reported by Abbott & Doenhoff [2], like shown in Fig. 3.2 and Fig. 3.3. The data have been recorded in the Langley Two-Dimensional Low-Turbulence tunnel. The calculated aerodynamic efficiency is shown in Fig. 3.4.

3.1.3 Wind tunnel data comparison

Section lift coefficient

It can be seen that the calculated values of the section lift coefficient show excellent agreement with the wind tunnel data at low angle of attack α . For higher α values, the experimental data for the standard roughness airfoil presents an early stall condition, while

α [°]	c_l	c_d	E	Iterations
0	-0,000071	0,009723	-0,01	2000
2	0,223562	0,010210	21,90	2000
4	0,442413	0,011793	37,51	2000
6	0,652675	0,014499	45,02	2000
8	0,850201	0,018494	45,97	2000
10	1,031193	0,023617	43,66	2000
12	1,187787	0,030342	39,15	2000
14	1,307339	0,039119	33,42	2000
16	1,409167	0,048345	29,15	4000
18	1,446891	0,061460	23,54	4000
20	1,265809	0,099153	12,77	4000

Table v. NACA 0012 airfoil, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

the smooth airfoil with natural transition reaches higher values of c_{lmax} and α_{st} . The calculated values in proximity of the stall are located between the smooth surface airfoil curves and the standard roughness airfoil curve. The maximum section lift coefficient is a little lower than the one measured on a profile with smooth surface and natural transition at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$, while the α_{st} results a little higher.

Section drag coefficient

The effects of the turbulent flow are more evident in the $c_d - c_l$ plot, where the imposed transition by the standard roughness leads to higher values of c_d respect to the smooth surface and natural transition conditions. For small α values the code calculations are in excellent agreement with the wind tunnel data for the airfoil with standard roughness.

Stalling characteristics

In general, thin sections and sections with small camber at high Reynolds numbers show rather abrupt stall, and the NACA 0012 section belongs to this category. In the rough surface conditions many airfoils have good stalling characteristics at most Reynolds numbers, but the NACA 0012 is an exception because even in the rough condition it shows undesirable stalling characteristics. The stall condition is a critical issue for CFD simulation, but the STAR-CCM+ solver is able to show this behavior in the right way.

Efficiency

The calculated aerodynamic efficiency at $\alpha = 8^\circ$ is $E = 45,97$.

Figure 3.2. NACA 0012 airfoil, $c_l - \alpha$ curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.3. NACA 0012 airfoil, $c_d - c_l$ polar curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.4. NACA 0012 airfoil, lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α , Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

3.1.4 CFD data comparison

Two further cases were run to compare the STAR-CCM+ solver results with other CFD solvers, following the recent work of Imamura[12].

Laminar flow at $Re = 500$

In this case, a laminar flow at $Re = 500$ and angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$ around the NACA 0012 airfoil was modeled.

A first attempt was made with the model chord length equal to 1 m, but the very low values of Mach number and free stream velocity caused convergence problems and undesired crash. A second attempt was made scaling the original mesh by a 0,001 factor, so that the model chord length was reduced to 0,001 m . This procedure granted excellent results.

The Table VI compares the published results and the STAR-CCM+ simulation. The GILBM is a Lattice Boltzmann Method on generalized coordinates, CFL3D is a Navier-Stokes solver using the finite volume formulation on generalized coordinates and PowerFLOW is a commercially available LBM solver.

A comparative study between PowerFLOW and CFL3D, based on the NACA 0012 airfoil, can be found in ref. [21].

The STAR-CCM+ solver shows excellent agreement with the other computational methods in this relatively low Reynolds number case.

The section lift coefficient is rightly close to vanish, as expected for symmetrical airfoils when the angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$.

The small error is probably due to the generated mesh which is not perfectly symmetrical.

Solver	Grid size	c_d	c_l
GILBM	257×65	0,1736	$1,0e-13$
GILBM	373×141	0,1725	$1,0e-13$
PowerFLOW	159 060	0,1717	$0,227e-3$
PowerFLOW	418 800	0,1807	$-0,211e-3$
CFL3D	257×65	0,1762	$0,115e-6$
CFL3D	373×141	0,1741	$0,538e-5$
STAR-CCM+	30 105	0,1788	$0,423e-5$

Table VI. NACA 0012 airfoil, CFD codes comparison for laminar flow at $Re = 500$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ$

Turbulent flow at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^5$

In this case, a turbulent flow at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^5$ and angle of attack $\alpha = 7^\circ$ around the NACA 0012 airfoil was modeled.

The Table VII compares the published results and the STAR-CCM+ simulation while a streamlines and pressure distribution plot is shown in Fig.3.5.

The STAR-CCM+ solution is in excellent agreement with Imamura’s GILBM, and pretty close to the CFL3D solution. As just observed by Imamura, the PowerFLOW solution overpredicted the drag coefficient.

Solver	Grid size	c_d	c_l
GILBM (Baldwin-Lomax Model)	16 705	0,0177	0,6979
CFL3D (Spalart-Allmaras Model)	16 705	0,0157	0,7449
PowerFLOW	800 000	0,028	0,63
STAR-CCM+ (Spalart-Allmaras Model)	30 105	0,0177	0,6977

Table VII. NACA 0012 airfoil, CFD codes comparison for turbulent flow at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^5$ and $\alpha = 7^\circ$

Figure 3.5. NACA 0012 airfoil, pressure contour and streamlines, STAR-CCM+ simulation of turbulent flow at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^5$ and $\alpha = 7^\circ$

3.2 The NACA 2412 wing section

The NACA 2412 profile has 2% camber at 40% of the chord from the leading edge and is 12% thick. The first two integers taken together define the mean line, in this case the NACA 24 mean line, while the thickness distribution is the same of the NACA 0012 symmetrical airfoil.

The Table VIII shows the ordinates and the Fig. 3.6 reproduces the NACA 2412 wing section profile.

Upper surface		Lower surface	
Station	Ordinate	Station	Ordinate
0	—	0	0
1,25	2,15	1,25	-1,65
2,5	2,99	2,5	-2,27
5,0	4,13	5,0	-3,01
7,5	4,96	7,5	-3,46
10	5,63	10	-3,75
15	6,61	15	-4,10
20	7,26	20	-4,23
25	7,67	25	-4,22
30	7,88	30	-4,12
40	7,80	40	-3,80
50	7,24	50	-3,34
60	6,36	60	-2,76
70	5,18	70	-2,14
80	3,75	80	-1,50
90	2,08	90	-0,82
95	1,14	95	-0,48
100	(0,13)	100	(-0,13)
100	—	100	0

L.E. radius: 1,58
Slope of radius through L.E.: 0,10

Table VIII. NACA 2412 airfoil section, stations and ordinates given in percent of airfoil chord

Figure 3.6. NACA 2412 airfoil

The NACA 2412 is a lifting airfoil with good stall characteristics in both smooth and

rough condition. We chose this airfoil because of the large amount of recent experimental data and because it has a similar thickness distribution to the Clark Y airfoil. In fact, well known airfoils of a certain class, including the Göttingen 398 and the Clark Y, which have been proved to be efficient, are nearly alike when their camber is removed (mean line straightened) and they are reduced to the same maximum thickness. A thickness variation similar to that of these airfoils was therefore chosen for the development of the NACA airfoils, like extensively described by Jacobs and Ward [14].

3.2.1 Simulation results

The simulation results in terms of the aerodynamic section lift coefficient, section drag coefficient and efficiency are shown in Table IX

The data have been compared with the experimental wind tunnel measures recorded in the Langley two-dimensional low-turbulence tunnel and reported by Abbott, Doenhoff and Stivers [1], like shown in Fig. 3.7 and Fig. 3.8. The calculated aerodynamic efficiency is shown in Fig. 3.9.

α [°]	c_l	c_d	E
-6	-0,426467	0,014114	-30,2151
-4	-0,215383	0,011648	-18,4903
-2	0,002760	0,010442	0,2642
0	0,223108	0,010598	21,0525
2	0,441764	0,011970	36,9047
4	0,654954	0,014379	45,5483
6	0,856434	0,018107	47,2989
8	1,048507	0,022594	46,4063
10	1,220531	0,028436	42,9223
12	1,369830	0,035733	38,3355
14	1,491552	0,044346	33,6345
16	1,570985	0,054567	28,7898
18	1,574889	0,068410	23,0212
20	1,442493	0,095860	15,0479

Table IX. NACA 2412 airfoil, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

3.2.2 Wind tunnel data comparison

Section lift coefficient

In this case, the STAR-CCM+ results are in excellent agreement with the experimental data trough the whole angle of attack range. The c_{lmax} and α_{st} are just slightly overestimated.

Section drag coefficient

In the $c_d - c_l$ polar plot the calculated results show the same effect followed by the experimental data for natural transition when the Reynolds number increases. The available standard roughness data has been recorded at $Re = 6 \cdot 10^6$ and a direct comparison is not possible, nevertheless the results seem reasonably good.

Stalling characteristics

The NACA 2412 has a little more gentle stalling characteristics than the NACA 0012, the STAR-CCM+ solver seems to model in the right way the approaching stall condition.

Efficiency

The calculated aerodynamic efficiency at $\alpha = 6^\circ$ is $E = 45,3$.

Figure 3.7. NACA 2412 airfoil, $c_l - \alpha$ curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.8. NACA 2412 airfoil, $c_d - c_l$ polar curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.9. NACA 2412 airfoil, lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α , Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

3.3 The Clark Y wing section

Virginius E. Clark designed the famous Clark Y airfoil in 1922, at the very beginning of aeronautics, nevertheless it still represents an excellent low subsonic airfoil. It has been used by aviation's pioneers, for instance Charles Lindbergh had a Clark Y wing on his Spirit of St. Louis, but many other military and civil airplanes between the 20's and the 50's flew with this airfoil. It also found large applications in propellers design thanks to the flat bottom which simplified the manufacturing process. More recently it has been used for model airplanes and for aerobatic parachutes and parafoils. It's not surprising to discover it today as a potential candidate for highly efficient power kites.

The Table x shows the ordinates and the Fig. 3.10 reproduces the Clark Y wing section profile.

Upper surface		Lower surface	
Station	Ordinate	Station	Ordinate
0	3,50	0	3,50
1,25	5,45	1,25	1,93
2,5	6,50	2,5	1,47
5,0	7,90	5,0	0,93
7,5	8,85	7,5	0,63
10	9,60	10	0,42
15	10,68	15	0,15
20	11,36	20	0,03
30	11,70	30	0,00
40	11,40	40	0,00
50	10,52	50	0,00
60	9,15	60	0,00
70	7,35	70	0,00
80	5,22	80	0,00
90	2,80	90	0,00
95	1,49	95	0,00
100	0,12	100	0,00
L.E. radius: 1,50			

Table x. Standard Clark Y airfoil section, stations and ordinates given in percent of airfoil chord

A certain care is needed when defining the angle of attack α because the original standard chord direction is aligned to the flat bottom profile, and in this work we always refer to this definition. This could be somehow misleading following the usual chord definition of straight line connecting the leading edge and the trailing edge, in fact the two chord definitions differ one another $1^{\circ}59'$. A third choice could be made considering the zero lift free stream direction and then starting measuring from this direction the so called "absolute angle of attack". Unfortunately the zero lift direction varies with the Reynolds

Figure 3.10. Standard Clark Y airfoil

number and with the Mach number, so even if this reference system is extremely useful to compare the characteristics of different airfoils, it could be confusing when calculating the force coefficients.

3.3.1 Experimental data source and interpretation

The Clark Y airfoil has been extensively tested in several wind tunnels when the design of the experimental facilities was making the first steps. Following the data published by NACA between the 20's and the 40's is a kind of time travel, unfortunately the data accuracy is poor, nevertheless it's always possible to understand the qualitative behavior of the airfoil. The best available and more recent experimental measures by NACA seem to be the ones reported by the NACA-TR-669 [15] and the NACA-TR-502 [25]. The first Report illustrates the final correction to a wide range of data collected during twenty years of measures in the Langley Variable Density Tunnel (V.D.T.), the second one compares measures from the Full Scale Tunnel (F.S.T.). In both cases, the two-dimensional section data were extrapolated from the measured data on a finite span wing model of aspect ratio equal to 6. Unfortunately, the measures obtained some years later with the Two-Dimensional Low-Turbulence Pressure Tunnel on the NACA series showed that the previous methods were inadequate to predict the two-dimensional section data, see NACA-TN-1283 for full details [30].

3.3.2 Simulation settings and results

The same settings used for the turbulent flow past the NACA 0012 airfoil at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ have been applied to this case, with the only difference that a finer two dimensional volume mesh with 64 041 cells has been used to improve the results accuracy. The simulation results are shown in Table XI, were we also reported the section pitching moment coefficient referred to a point located at 25 percent of the chord. The results have been compared with the experimental wind tunnel measures recorded in the Langley variable-density tunnel

and in the full-scale tunnel like shown in Fig. 3.11 and Fig. 3.12. The calculated aerodynamic efficiency is shown in Fig. 3.13.

α [°]	c_l	c_d	$c_{m_{c/4}}$	E
-6	-0,068555	0,011860	-0,078934	-5,7804
-4	0,146491	0,010834	-0,078392	13,5215
-2	0,366288	0,011170	-0,078640	32,7930
0	0,585605	0,012992	-0,079281	45,0739
2	0,801316	0,015835	-0,080152	50,6044
4	1,008785	0,019661	-0,081132	51,3101
6	1,202819	0,024769	-0,081787	48,5623
8	1,379125	0,031083	-0,081996	44,3686
10	1,533132	0,038588	-0,081774	39,7312
12	1,657004	0,047540	-0,080114	34,8551
14	1,734089	0,058231	-0,075239	29,7797
16	1,743243	0,071472	-0,066718	24,3904
18	1,631352	0,095276	-0,059093	17,1224

Table XI. ClarkY airfoil, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

3.3.3 Wind tunnel data comparison

Section lift coefficient

We just anticipated the low accuracy of the two dimensional extrapolated data, and it is difficult in this particular test case to estimate the solver accuracy. In fact, the experimental curves also highly differ one another.

The following quotations from [25] apply to both two dimensional and three dimensional flow condition: “...the variable-density-tunnel results are from 10 to 13 percent higher than those from the full-scale tunnel at the same Reynolds Numbers. This difference between variable-density and full-scale tunnel maximum lift coefficients is believed to be largely due to the unlike turbulences in the two tunnels...” and “Several experimenters have shown that one of the effect of turbulence on medium-cambered medium-thick airfoils, such as the Clark Y, is to increase the maximum lift coefficient.”

The presented data from the V.D.T. need a final remark regarding the so called “effective Reynolds number”. The experimental turbulence measurements on the V.D.T. stream suggested to apply a correction to the measured Reynolds number, so tests at $Re = 3,17 \cdot 10^6$ on the three dimensional wing were considered at “effective” $Re = 8,37 \cdot 10^6$ to extrapolate the infinite aspect ratio characteristics, i.e. the profile force coefficients.

The STAR-CCM+ results show a higher lift curve slope c_{l_α} respect to the experimental data. Nevertheless, approaching the stall condition the fully turbulent results follow a smoother curve, leading to $c_{l_{max}}$ and α_{st} values only slightly overestimated respect to the

variable-density tunnel measures. We have good reasons to consider these data closer to the simulated fully turbulent condition than the full-scale tunnel data.

Section drag coefficient

In the $c_d - c_l$ polar plot the calculated results have a behavior somehow similar to the previous test cases. Where data are available for comparison, the old measures collected in the variable-density tunnel are close to the generally accepted measures in the two-dimensional low-turbulence tunnel. The data from the full scale tunnel seem to be affected by lower accuracy. Even if we didn't find standard roughness data for the Clark Y airfoil, the calculated magnitude of the minimum drag coefficient increase respect to the free transition condition is comparable with other airfoils.

The Table XII illustrates this issue.

Airfoil	Wind Tunnel	Free transition (experimental) c_{dmin}	Standard Roughness (experimental) c_{dmin}	Fully turbulent STAR-CCM+ c_{dmin}
NACA 0012	T.D.T	0,0058	0,0098	0,009723
NACA 0012	V.D.T.	0,0060		
NACA 2412	T.D.T	0,0064	0,0099	0,010442
NACA 2412	V.D.T	0,0061		
Clark Y	F.S.T.	0,0083		0,010834
Clark Y	V.D.T.	0,0072		

Table XII. Calculated and experimental c_{dmin} for different airfoils

Stalling characteristics

In a recent work Broeren and Bragg [6] carried out low turbulence wind tunnel measurements at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^5$, showing that the Clark Y airfoil presents in those conditions a combination of trailing-edge and leading-edge stall type. Following this work we learn that during the experiment the mean lift gradually decreased beyond stall until $\alpha = 19^\circ$, where an abrupt drop occurred, being this behavior characteristics of leading-edge stall. We run the simulation at a higher Reynolds number, but the solver similarly showed a gentle decrease after the stall, located in our case approximately at $\alpha = 16^\circ$.

Efficiency

The calculated aerodynamic efficiency at $\alpha = 4^\circ$ is $E = 51,3$. From Fig. 3.13 it can be seen that the fully turbulent condition, having as a primary effect the drag coefficient increase, causes a reduction and a shift to a lower angle of attack of the maximum aerodynamic efficiency.

Figure 3.11. Clark Y airfoil, $c_l - \alpha$ curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.12. Clark Y airfoil, $c_d - c_l$ polar curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.13. Clark Y airfoil, lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α , STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

3.4 The Clark Y rectangular wing

To complete the series of test cases we run the three dimensional simulation of a fully turbulent flow past a rectangular wing having the Clark Y base section. The virtual model have 1 m chord length and 6 m span, the resulting aspect ratio is equal to 6. Since we tested only symmetrical flow conditions, i.e. with the free stream direction lying on the wing symmetry plane, it was possible to split the wing in two parts and model only one half of the wing applying a symmetrical boundary condition. This procedure obviously reduces the RAM memory requirements and cuts down the computational time. The resulting volume mesh has 2 052 721 cells.

The simulation results for $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ are shown in Table XIII. The results have been compared with experimental data like shown from Fig. 3.15 to Fig. 3.18.

α [°]	C_L	C_D	E
-8,5	-0,211630	0,012877	-16,4344
0	0,464825	0,011546	40,2595
10	1,202203	0,088471	13,5887
14	1,405738	0,139386	10,0852
16	1,483703	0,169197	8,7691
18	1,539985	0,200936	7,6641

Table XIII. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

3.4.1 Wind tunnel data comparison

Wing lift coefficient

The available experimental data for the finite span wing have been directly measured on the scale model, so they don't suffer for the extrapolation process which affects the infinite aspect ratio data. Nevertheless, a different behavior still characterizes the two curves, like shown in Fig. 3.15. It's clearly visible that the data from the full scale tunnel present an early stall condition and a lower C_{Lmax} value.

The simulation results have a slightly higher lift curve slope $C_{L\alpha}$, but approaching the stall condition the C_{Lmax} almost corresponds to the variable density tunnel measurements. The determination of the pre and post stall behavior would have required some more simulations in that angle of attack range, but considering the computational cost of the three dimensional simulations we decided that the check test for this case was satisfying enough.

Wing drag coefficient

The wing drag coefficient comparison requires some interesting remarks. As can be seen from Fig. 3.16 and Fig. 3.17, the results are in general very good, being located approximately in the middle of the experimental curves. The only exception is represented by the run at angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$, where the simulation showed some convergence problem. We didn't find proofs of a meshing or setting problem, so we can only suppose that a numerical problem arose for this particular case because the free stream direction and the outer boundaries of the computational domain are perfectly aligned to the profile flat bottom. The corresponding residual plot is shown in Fig. 3.14.

It can be clearly seen that the residual of the momentum component along the Z direction, which in our case is aligned to the wing span direction, didn't reduce anymore after the first 500 iterations.

Figure 3.14. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, residuals plot, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ$

Looking now to the C_D numerical values, they are obviously higher than in the two dimensional wing section case because of the induced drag component.

Efficiency

The aerodynamic efficiency is again in excellent agreement with the experimental data plotted in Fig. 3.18, except for the $E = 40,25$ value corresponding to $\alpha = 0^\circ$. This particular result is greatly affected by the poor convergence problem we previously pointed out.

Figure 3.15. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, $C_L - \alpha$ curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.16. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, $C_D - \alpha$ curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.17. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, $C_D - C_L$ polar curve, STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

Figure 3.18. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α , STAR-CCM+ simulations and wind tunnel data comparison

3.4.2 Pressure maps and streamlines

The STAR-CCM+ solver offers a wide choice of options to visualize the results. For instance in Fig. 3.19 are represented the streamlines and the tip vortex responsible for the induced drag component at $\alpha = 18^\circ$, a condition almost close to the stall. In Fig. 3.20 and in Fig. 3.21 are shown the pressure contour maps respectively on the upper and on the lower wing surface.

Figure 3.19. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, streamlines, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 3.20. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, pressure contour, upper surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 3.21. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 6, pressure contour, lower surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Chapter 4

The kite model

4.1 Low aspect ratio rectangular wing

A preliminary simulation of the flow past a rectangular wing sharing the same geometrical dimensions of a real kite has been used as a benchmark to investigate the changes in terms of force and moment coefficients when the kite curvature in the YZ plane is added.

The general dimensions of the wing are listed in Table XIV while a rendered CAD model is shown in Fig. 4.1.

Airfoil	Clark Y	
Chord	2,18	m
Span	7,34	m
Planform area	16	m ²
Aspect ratio	3,367	
Mass	2,1	kg
Center of mass		
X_{COM}	0,91919	m
Y_{COM}	0,10578	m
Z_{COM}	0	m

Table XIV. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367 , geometrical and mass properties

4.1.1 STAR-CCM+ simulation settings

The actual dimensions of the wing have been used, so the free stream velocity has been adjusted to give the same Reynolds number used for the previous simulations.

The control volume has been created so that along the X direction there are 3 chord lengths in front of the leading edge and 5 chord lengths past the trailing edge, along the Y direction there are 5 chord lengths above and below the wing, along the Z direction there are 3 chord lengths over the wing tip. Once again, the volume mesh represents only one half of the wing thanks to the symmetrical flow and geometrical conditions.

Figure 4.1. Clark Y rectangular wing

Only a few simulations were run, investigating at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ where we reasonably expected the maximum lift to drag ratio, and at angles of attack in proximity of the stall condition. The following conditions have been applied:

$$Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$$

$$\rho = 1,225 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\text{chord} = 2,18 \text{ m}$$

$$V_\infty = 20,1 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\mu = 1,79 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa/s}$$

$$p = 1,01325 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$T = 288,2 \text{ K}$$

3D steady and stationary viscous flow

Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model

smooth wall surface, no-slip

mesh size 2 041 721 volume cells

computational domain $19,62 \times 21,8 \times 10,21 = 4367 \text{ m}^3$

The number of iterations has been limited to 1000, in fact for all the simulated flow directions the convergence was just acceptable, being the residuals in the range from 10^{-2} to 10^{-4} and showing a decreasing trend.

The calculated force and moment coefficients are shown in Table xv and plotted in Fig. 4.2. It can be seen from the plots that the stall condition has not been reached, in fact even if the $C_{L\alpha}$ slope is decreasing, the value is still positive and there is no evidence of sudden drag rise in the corresponding $C_D - C_L$ polar curve.

The pressure coefficient distribution along the wing span at several sections starting from the XY symmetry plane (section $Z = 0$ m) and finishing in close proximity to the wing tip (section $Z = 3,66$ m) are presented from Fig. 4.3 to Fig. 4.5. As usual, the C_p distribution has been plotted against a dimensionless unitary chord. The $\alpha = 18^\circ$ value, close to the wing stall condition, determines a huge suction peak in the central sections of the wing. Since the wing has no twist, it is clearly visible that proceeding towards the wing tips the combined effects of the downwash and of the downward induced flow effectively decrease the camber and the angle of attack, reducing the section lift coefficient.

The continuous pressure distribution relative to the environmental static pressure is shown in Fig. 4.6 and in Fig. 4.7 for the upper and for the lower wing surface respectively.

The tip vortex behavior is clearly visible in Fig. 4.8. The relatively low aspect ratio magnifies the phenomenon respect to the wing with aspect ratio 6. A full description of the vortex system for a finite span wing can be found in McCormick [23].

α [°]	C_L	C_D	$C_{M_{c/4}}$	E
0	0,375491	0,014997	-0,069058	25,0375
10	1,002735	0,100520	-0,071473	9,9754
14	1,203758	0,156951	-0,075835	7,6696
16	1,288645	0,190830	-0,079792	6,7529
18	1,357663	0,227713	-0,084721	5,9622

Table xv. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367 , Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.2. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367, $C_L - \alpha$ curve and $C_D - C_L$ polar curve, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.3. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367 , pressure coefficient distribution along the span, sections at $Z = 0$ m and $Z = 0,75$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.4. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367 , pressure coefficient distribution along the span, sections at $Z = 1,5$ m and $Z = 2,25$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.5. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367 , pressure coefficient distribution along the span, sections at $Z = 3$ m and $Z = 3,66$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.6. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367, pressure contour, upper surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.7. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367, pressure contour, lower surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.8. Clark Y rectangular wing, aspect ratio 3,367, streamlines, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

4.2 Low aspect ratio kite

The existing rectangular wing has been virtually curved into a circular arc shape with a curvature radius equal to 4,673 m and a breadth of 90° . As a consequence, the projected area reduced and the center of mass moved downward. However, even if the planform area could be used as a reference area to define the force and moment coefficients, we still used the rectangular wing planform area.

The general dimensions are listed in Table XVI while a draft and a rendered CAD model are respectively shown in Fig. 4.9 and Fig. 4.10.

Airfoil	Clark Y	
Chord	2,18	m
Span	6,969	m
Planform area	14,956	m ²
Aspect ratio	3,197	
Mass	2,1	kg
Center of mass		
X_{COM}	0,91775	m
Y_{COM}	-0,37116	m
Z_{COM}	0	m

Table XVI. Clark Y kite, geometrical and mass properties

Figure 4.9. Clark Y kite

Figure 4.10. Clark Y kite

4.2.1 Simulation settings and results

The same settings used for the previous simulation have been applied to the kite model. The only existing difference is that the resulting mesh has 2 363 354 volume cells, being this due to the slightly different geometry.

The investigated angle of attack range is reasonably wide, so that it is possible to interpolate the needed data for further analysis. The simulation results are presented in Table xvii and plotted from Fig. 4.11 to Fig. 4.13.

α [°]	C_L	C_D	$C_{M_{c/4}}$	E
-8,5	-0,147145	0,010120	-0,068776	-14,5393
0	0,332445	0,013025	-0,062255	25,5232
6	0,652710	0,048509	-0,057211	13,4553
10	0,838511	0,083921	-0,053186	9,9916
14	0,990132	0,128428	-0,048977	7,7096
16	1,052356	0,154072	-0,047311	6,8303
18	1,084836	0,181022	-0,044766	5,9928
20	1,032335	0,218830	-0,056895	4,7175
Reference area $S = 16 \text{ m}^2$				

Table xvii. Clark Y kite, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

It's important to remark that adding a curvature in the YZ plane causes a variation of the wing section shape when the cutting planes are parallel to the XY plane. It is clearly visible from Fig. 4.14 that the absolute thickness of the wing sections increases proceeding towards the wing tip. This changes, together with the different vertical position of the sections along the span, are both responsible for the flow changes respect to the rectangular wing.

The pressure coefficients along the span are shown from Fig. 4.15 to Fig. 4.17. It can be noted that at the same angle of attack, respect to the rectangular wing, the suction peak at every section is a little lower. Nevertheless, the stall would happen just a few minutes later, in fact the simulation results at $\alpha = 20^\circ$ show all the stall characteristics.

For direct comparison with the rectangular wing, the pressure distribution is shown in Fig. 4.18 and in Fig. 4.19 for the upper and for the lower wing surface respectively. The streamlines are represented in Fig. 4.20.

Figure 4.11. Clark Y kite, $C_L - \alpha$ curve and $C_D - \alpha$ curve, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.12. Clark Y kite, $C_D - C_L$ polar curve, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.13. Clark Y kite, lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α , Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.14. Clark Y kite, absolute maximum thickness variation along the span

Figure 4.15. Clark Y kite, pressure coefficient distribution along the span, sections at $Z = 0$ m and $Z = 0,75$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.16. Clark Y kite, pressure coefficient distribution along the span, sections at $Z = 1,5$ m and $Z = 2,25$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.17. Clark Y kite, pressure coefficient distribution along the span, section at $Z = 3$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.18. Clark Y kite, pressure contour, upper surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.19. Clark Y kite, pressure contour, lower surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

Figure 4.20. Clark Y kite, streamlines, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 18^\circ$

4.2.2 Stalling characteristics

It can be seen from Fig. 4.21 that a separated flow zone detaches from the trailing edge of the kite at $\alpha = 20^\circ$. Furthermore, from Fig. 4.22 and Fig. 4.23 it is also clear that the pressure can't immediately recover the existing value in the outer flow. The initial stalling zone seems to be close to the center of the kite. A trailing edge separation is progressive with the angle of attack and results in a more gradual stalling.

Anyway, it's always necessary to remember that we run a steady flow simulation, while the stall is a highly unsteady phenomenon, so from our analysis we can just predict a general behavior. The location of the separation point, the stall angle of attack and the stall propagation are all time dependant parameter and their definition is over the purview of this preliminary study.

Figure 4.21. Clark Y kite, streamlines, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 20^\circ$

Figure 4.22. Clark Y kite, pressure coefficient, section at $Z = 0,75$ m, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 20^\circ$

Figure 4.23. Clark Y kite, pressure contour, upper surface, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulation at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$ and $\alpha = 20^\circ$

4.3 Wings comparison

We can finally compare the results from the simulation of the two rectangular wings and of the kite. Now it will be clear why we used for the kite the same reference area of the low aspect ratio wing. In fact, proceeding this way, the existing ratio between the resulting force components acting on the low aspect ratio wing and on the kite is directly readable from the coefficient plots. This is not true for the aspect ratio 6 wing, which has a different reference area.

Aspect ratio's effects

We found the expected result that the $C_{L\alpha}$ slope and the C_{Lmax} value decrease with a decreasing aspect ratio, like shown in Fig. 4.24.

We also verified that the drag coefficient C_D results proportional to the lift coefficient C_L in a predictable way, like it can be read from the polar curve plot in Fig. 4.25. It's remarkable that in the angle of attack range close to the maximum aerodynamic efficiency, readable from Fig. 4.26, the advantage in terms of efficiency of a high aspect ratio wing reduces. The reason can be obviously researched into a minor contribution of the induced drag to the total drag when the lift is small. In fact for the low aspect ratio wing there is a certain loss in terms of aerodynamic efficiency at high angle of attack respect to the aspect ratio 6 wing.

Finally, it seems that a fully turbulent flow could operate a beneficial effect respect to the natural transition condition when looking for a higher efficiency at small lift coefficient values.

Kite's curvature effects

The kite's curvature in the YZ plane reduces just a little the kite's aspect ratio, but the resulting shape has a detrimental effect on the $C_{L\alpha}$ slope and on the C_{Lmax} value. Nevertheless, the kite's aerodynamic efficiency curve is almost identical to the low aspect ratio wing's efficiency curve.

We know that a rectangular wing can't easily fly because of his inherent stability characteristics, while we learn by experience that circular arc kites show good and controllable flying qualities. The loss in lift is probably the price to be paid when looking for stability and control.

Figure 4.24. $C_L - \alpha$ curve for different wings, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.25. $C_D - C_L$ polar curve for different wings, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 4.26. Lift to drag ratio E vs angle of attack α for different wings, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model, STAR-CCM+ simulations at $Re = 3 \cdot 10^6$

Chapter 5

Kite equilibrium

In the previous chapter we obtained the aerodynamic characteristics of a kite with circular arc shape, now we present a way to determine the kite attitude as a function of the bridle lengths. We followed the same approach of Alexander and Stevenson [4] for a kite having the aerodynamic characteristics of a flat plate, but we proceeded making all the necessary changes needed to model a thick and cambered wing with curvature in the YZ plane.

For simplicity we only considered a wind blowing horizontally, but it is always possible to add a vertical velocity component to the wind. It's important to remark that the following results are only modeling the kite behavior in a steady state, similar to the well known attitude that the kite can assume at the edges of the wind window, resting at a fixed position relative to the ground. The case of a kite fast moving respect to the ground, experiencing an apparent wind like a sailing yacht, like it could be the case for a kite flying following the figure eight trajectory, it's definitely more complex involving inertial force components and requiring the dynamic equilibrium equations.

Nevertheless, some preliminary indications about the way to trim a power kite by mean of the bridles can be found with the following treatment.

5.1 Longitudinal static equilibrium

We introduce first of all the simplified model of the bridles configuration shown in Fig. 5.1. The kite has only two control lines connected to the bridle points. For simplicity only a front and a rear bridles depart from each bridle point and we assume that each bridle point lies on a plane containing the respective wing tip chord and parallel to the XY symmetry plane. This hypothesis it's more than acceptable when the control lines are particularly long respect to the kite dimensions. This scheme is somehow similar to the one used for leading edge inflatable kites having only two control lines, which don't need a complex bridles system to maintain their flying shape.

Furthermore, the front and rear bridles have not been fastened to the kite leading and trailing edges like in the cited article, but the front bridle connection is at 10 percent of the wing tip section chord, while the rear bridle is located at 75 percent of the same chord. A similar arrangement is used for instance when the kite have a tapered planform or when

the inlets of the inflatable vanes are obtained cutting off a portion of the leading edge.

Since we are studying only the longitudinal static equilibrium, the control lines and the bridles can be regarded as superimposed on the central vertical plane XY. This issue must be remembered when considering the tension acting on a single line.

Figure 5.1. Perspective view of the bridles simplified model

Adopting where possible the same nomenclature used by the cited authors, we briefly introduce the three forms of lift to drag ratio and the kite line angle:

$L/D = C_L/C_D$: lift to drag ratio of the kite aerodynamic surface alone;

$LTD = (L - Mg)/D$: corrected lift to drag ratio at the kite, taking kite weight into account;

$\theta_k = \arctan(LTD)$: kite line angle or azimuth angle at the kite bridle taking kite weight in account;

LTD_g : effective lift to drag ratio at the ground.

The forces acting on the kite wing are shown in Fig. 5.2, where the meaning of the symbols is as follow:

COM : kite center of mass;

COP : kite center of pressure;

$c/4$: point at one quarter of the reference chord;

R : resultant aerodynamic force;

Mg : kite weight;

B : bridle point.

Figure 5.2. Forces acting on the kite (left side view)

We chose the chord of the wing section laying on the XY symmetry plane as a reference chord for the whole wing. The $c/4$ point belong to this chord and the wing moment coefficient $C_{M_{c/4}}$ has been calculated with the $c/4$ point as a pole.

The first important remark is that for the arc shaped kite the center of mass is below the dashed reference chord. The center of mass position has been approximated considering a constant density for the kite volume, but it could be obviously calculated or measured with more accuracy if needed.

Figure 5.3. Forces equilibrium (left side view)

As can be seen from Fig. 5.3, the line tension T_e can be easily determined. In fact, from

$$b = R \cdot \cos(\arctan(L/D))$$

and

$$h = \sqrt{R^2 - b^2}$$

it follows that

$$T_e = \sqrt{(h - Mg)^2 + b^2}$$

The corresponding azimuth angle θ_k is given by

$$\theta_k = \arctan\left(\frac{h - Mg}{b}\right)$$

while the angle of the kite to the line γ is simply

$$\gamma = \theta_k + \alpha$$

At first sight, the role of the angle of attack α in the previous equations could escape. In reality lift and drag change with α and have a major influence on the line tension T_e . We now need to grant the moments equilibrium, but here we don't follow [4] anymore. Since the $c/4$ point and the center of mass are not moving respect to the kite and we just

have calculated the moment coefficient of the aerodynamic force respect to the $c/4$ point, with reference to Fig. 5.4 we can write

$$M_{c/4} + Mg \cos \alpha \cdot l - Mg \sin \alpha \cdot m + T_e \cdot n = 0$$

which can be solved for n where

l : moment arm length for Mg force component normal to the chord from $c/4$ point;

m : moment arm length for Mg force component parallel to the chord from $c/4$ point;

n : moment arm length for line force T_e from $c/4$ point.

While the l and m moment arm length are constant and positive, the n moment arm length can vary and it assumes a positive value when T_e generates a clockwise moment respect to the $c/4$ point pole. It's also important to remember that the calculated $C_{M_{c/4}}$ for the kite is negative when the C_L is positive.

Figure 5.4. Moments equilibrium (left side view)

Figure 5.5. Construction to determine bridle length r (left side view)

With reference to Fig.5.5 we introduce the following absolute dimensions:

f : front bridle length;

x_f : front bridle connection position from the leading edge of the wing tip;

r : rear bridle length;

x_r : rear bridle connection position from the leading edge of the wing tip;

y : length of the perpendicular from the bridle point to the wing tip chord;

a : distance from the bridle point to the kite wing tip chord, along the line of the kite line;

v : vertical distance from the reference chord to the wing tip chord;

x_1 : distance from the point where the line would meet the chord to the front bridle connection;

x_2 : distance from the point where the line would meet the chord to the point where a perpendicular from the bridle point would meet the wing tip chord

We can now calculate the rear bridle length as a function of the front bridle length that grants the static equilibrium. First of all we calculate x_1 as

$$x_1 = x_{c/4} + \frac{n}{\sin \gamma} - \frac{v}{\tan \gamma} - x_f$$

then from the cosine rule

$$f^2 = a^2 + x_1^2 - 2ax_1 \cos \gamma$$

which can be solved for a :

$$a = \frac{2x_1 \cos \gamma + \sqrt{(-2x_1 \cos \gamma)^2 - 4(x_1^2 - f^2)}}{2}$$

Then

$$y = a \sin \gamma$$

and

$$x_2 = a \cos \gamma$$

Finally

$$r = \sqrt{y^2 + (x_r - x_f + x_2 - x_1)^2}$$

5.2 Numerical solution

A set of results is proposed in Table XVIII starting from the following initial data:

kite surface $S = 16 \text{ m}^2$

$\rho = 1,225 \text{ kg/m}^3$

wind speed $V = 5 \text{ m/s}$

kite chord $c = 2,18 \text{ m}$

kite weight $Mg = 34,335 \text{ N}$

$l = 0,37275 \text{ m}$

$m = 0,37116 \text{ m}$

$x_f = 0,218 \text{ m}$ (10% of the chord)

$x_r = 1,635 \text{ m}$ (75% of the chord)

$x_{c/4} = 0,545 \text{ m}$

$v = 1,369 \text{ m}$

front bridle $f = 1,635 \text{ m}$ (75% of the chord)

α [°]	L [N]	D [N]	$M_{c/4}$ [Nm]	R [N]	T_e [N]	θ_k [°]	r [m]	r/c
0	81,4	3,2	-33,3	81,5	57,7	86,1	1,755	0,805
2	107,6	4,9	-32,4	107,7	80,2	86,2	1,802	0,826
4	133,8	7,4	-31,5	134,0	104,5	85,8	1,797	0,825
6	159,9	11,9	-30,6	160,4	129,7	84,6	1,799	0,825
8	182,8	15,9	-29,5	183,5	152,0	83,9	1,770	0,812
10	205,4	20,6	-28,4	206,5	174,5	83,1	1,734	0,795
12	223,9	25,7	-27,3	225,4	193,0	82,3	1,699	0,779
14	242,6	31,5	-26,2	244,6	211,9	81,4	1,661	0,762
16	257,8	37,7	-25,3	260,6	227,6	80,4	1,626	0,746
18	265,8	44,4	-23,9	269,5	236,3	79,2	1,600	0,734
20	252,9	53,6	-30,4	258,5	226,3	76,2	1,610	0,739

Table XVIII. Rear bridle length calculation

The rear bridle length versus the azimuth angle is plotted in Fig. 5.6. The maximum θ_k for a wind blowing at 5 m/s is approximately $86,2^\circ$ with a rear bridle length measuring 82,6% of the chord. The maximum θ_k value is important because it's directly related to the maximum LTD attainable by the kite.

Examining the plot, it's immediately evident that in the low angle of attack range the same bridle configuration leads to different equilibrium attitudes. Even if we could always analyze if these equilibrium points are stable or unstable, we would probably prefer to avoid this kind of behavior in the whole angle of attack range before the stall. As can be seen from Fig. 5.7, a possible solution could be increasing the front bridle length over 150% of the chord, so that the equilibrium points become univocally determined.

The effect of increasing wind speed is quite evident, leading to a higher value of maximum θ_k . It can be also noted that the curve at 5 m/s is greatly shifted respect to the others. The reason must be researched considering the effect of the kite weight. In fact the magnitude of the resultant aerodynamic force and of the kite weight is comparable only at very low wind speed, while increasing the wind speed the weight becomes negligible.

Furthermore, we have the confirmation of what we know by experience that at fixed front bridle length, a higher angle of attack and a higher lift can be obtained reducing the rear bridle length.

5.3 Trimming

A power kite must operate on duty at variable wind speed, and its effective wind speed also greatly varies along the trajectory. Examining again the Fig. 5.7, we can conclude that a good trimming could be achieved with a bridle configuration that grants the target C_L and LTD at the maximum operational wind speed. With this trim strategy, the flight at lower wind speed is always possible. In fact, even if at a lower wind speed the kite has a lower LTD , the lift coefficient is however positive and increases when the wind speed decreases.

Considering a numerical example, let us assume the design parameters shown in Table XIX, where the front and rear bridles have the required length to grant the design lift coefficient at the design maximum wind speed.

Angle of attack α	8°
Lift coefficient C_L	0,746
Drag coefficient C_D	0,065
Lift to drag ratio L/D	11,47
Wind speed	60 m/s
LTD	11,43
Total lines tension (at bridle points)	26384 N
Front bridle length	150% of the chord
Rear bridle length	149,62% of the chord

Table XIX. Design point for a power kite

From the kite aerodynamic characteristics previously determined and from the study of the equilibrium points, it's easy to extract with a linear interpolation the kite angle of

attack as a function of the wind speed. Examining the resulting plot, shown in Fig. 5.8, we can conclude that the kite angle of attack decreases with increasing wind speed, but the slope of the curve is higher in the low wind speed range, while α changes little for the higher wind speeds.

This result is extremely important, because it grants high performances of the power kite for a wide range of flying conditions away from the design point. Even if the exact determination of the kite attitude will necessarily require to keep in account the dynamic equilibrium and other factors like cables parasite drag, the published results for the KiteGen project acquire greater validity, because we demonstrated that if the kite is flying at a sufficiently high speed, the preliminary hypothesis of a constant lift coefficient is not so far from reality.

Nevertheless this is not true for the slow speed range, so that the control model improvement still remains a critical element, being the slow speed conditions prevailing during the lift off procedure and during the recovery phase. The kite itself must be designed with the slow speed behavior always in mind.

Figure 5.6. Bridle lengths for static longitudinal equilibrium

Figure 5.7. Bridle lengths for static longitudinal equilibrium

Figure 5.8. Angle of attack α vs wind speed for fixed bridle lengths

Chapter 6

Conclusions

A first set of results obtained simulating the flow past an arc shaped wing with a RANS code has been presented. The same results have been used to calculate the static equilibrium of the wing when used as a tethered kite, investigating the separated effects of bridles configuration and wind speed changes. A first trimming strategy to grant the flight over a variable wind speed range has been also proposed.

A lot of work still remains, investigating first of all the effects of tapering the wing and increasing the curvature in the YZ plane. The performances of unconventional wing sections, like the ones used for LEI kites, should be analyzed, such as the effects of cutting the leading edge like in ram air kite. Since the KiteGen is intended to work at high altitude using extremely long control lines, the effects of the lines shall be carefully studied and integrated into the control model.

Modeling the behavior of the kite flying trough the power zone it's not an easy task, but it will be the necessary step to understand if a fast kite flying with a small lift coefficient or a slower kite with a higher lift coefficient will grant the maximum mean power generation during a cycle.

The acquisition of experimental measures from the prototypes will play in the immediate future a key role in understanding kite's flight dynamics, and from the comparison of computational and experimental data the KiteGen will hopefully turn into reality.

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